

Saint Nicholas "Maroulenas", Kastania, southern Greece, byzantine church

also known as "Eastern orthodox christian doctrine"

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The small byzantine church of Saint Nicholas "Maroulenas" is a fine example of the single-nave cross-vaulted (or traverse-vault) architectural type, dated in 13th century. It is located in the village of Kastania, in the messinian Mani, the south-western part of Messinia region, in the Peloponnese, southern Greece. Numerous churches of byzantine to post byzantine times are preserved within the village, marking it as a particular regional religious center. "Maroulena" is believed to have been the name of the female resident who lived nearby the church and took care of it. Despite its limited size and humble aspirations, the church is decorated by fine murals, dated in the end of the 13th century. The iconographic program includes the depiction of Theotokos in the apse, scenes from the Life of Saint Nicholas and of Christ Passion, saint figures etc. Both in style and iconography, conservatism and copying western trends are to be noticed. The church was purposed to function most probably for private (a family) or limited number of faithful (the members of the quarter) gatherings. It remained in use officially till the conquest of the Peloponnese by the Ottomans, in 1460. In the 18th century, an era of local economic development, the church restored its religious function and was redecorated by few new murals. Today, it is considered a monument of byzantine art, celebrating only in the Feast day of the patron saint, i.e. Saint Nicholas.

Date Range: 1200 CE - 2023 CE

Region: Kastania, messinian Mani, Messinia, Peloponnese, southern Greece

Region tags: Europe, Greece

Kastania is a medieval village, situated in the north of messinian Mani region.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Μ. Παναγιωτίδη, Οι τοιχογραφίες του Αγίου Νικολάου στη Μεγάλη Καστανία της Μεσσηνιακής Μάνης, 2ο Συμπόσιο Βυζαντινής και Μεταβυζαντινής Αρχαιολογίας, Αθήνα 1982, 80-81 (in Greek).

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://naoistimani.blogspot.com/p/blog-page_199.html

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Back in medieval times historical circumstances allowed for interaction with roman catholic religious groups (mainly Franks, in lesser extent in that region with Venetians). Compulsory "contact" was implemented by the dominance of the muslim Ottomans after 1460.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– Yes

Notes: Especially with the muslim Ottomans

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– Yes

Notes: There were constant fights between different ethnicities, and consecutively, with different religious groups.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Through the ceremony of Baptism. Nowadays, it is optionally.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: That is for modern era. To a great extent, it was compulsory at medieval times

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: Up to nowadays, religious affiliation through Baptism is traditionally assigned at very early years of life.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Through the ceremony of Baptism

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– I don't know

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– I don't know

Notes: It was attempted at medieval times

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Notes: There was always a strong connection between Orthodox Church and the (byzantine or modern Greek) State. Nowadays, political support to Church is still active but limited.

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– I don't know

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: Back in medieval times that must have been not an unusual phenomenon

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large religious group (unknown relationship to other religious groups, or presence of other religious groups unknown)

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: the priests

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– I don't know

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– Yes

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and

unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Notes: The Bible: The Old and the New Testament

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they oral:

– No

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Notes: The Bible contains a series of narrations related to the origin of many holy stories revealed to people.

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Notes: Archangels

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– I don't know

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Prrophets

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: the Apostles, Saints and other holy figures

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Can interpretation also take place outside these institutions:

– Yes

↳ Interpretation is only allowed by officially sanctioned figures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– Yes

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: There are many other byzantine churches in the village and in the whole region of Mani

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Notes: Monumental architecture includes churches built with different architectural types and decorated with wall paintings of several periods and styles

↳ Tombs:

– No

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– No

↳ Altars:

– Yes

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– No

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– I don't know

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Notes: The church is decorated by an extensive iconographic program of byzantine style, dated to the end of 13th century. There are also few paintings dated in the 18th century

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Archangels, angels

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: this probably refers to the scene of Christ's Transfiguration

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Notes: cross

- ↳ Humans:
 - Yes
 - Notes: saints, holy figures, common people

- ↳ Other features of iconography:
 - Yes
 - Notes: there is an extensive iconographic program. Main scenes depicted are from Christ and saint Nicholas' Life

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

- I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

- Yes

Notes: Nowadays, at the Feast Day of the church, that is the name day of saint Nicholas 6th of December.

- ↳ How strict is pilgrimage:
 - Optional (common)

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

- Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:
 - Yes

- ↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:
 - Yes

- ↳ Other spirit-body relationship:
 - I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The belief in afterlife is fundamental in christian religious thought and faith

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– Yes [specify]: known as Paradise and Hell

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Christian faith does not support reincarnation but resurrection

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Notes: The church was probably intended for private / family / small community religious practice. There is no indication of funerary function.

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Field doesn't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: salvation from sins

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– No

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

↳ Other purpose:

– Yes [specify]: Salvation from sins, resurrection of the dead, deliverance of souls

Is an eschatology present:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton in this lifetime:

– No

↳ Eschaton at specified time in future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in near future:

– No

↳ Eschaton at unspecified time in distant future:

– Yes

↳ Eschaton at some other time:

– I don't know

↳ Adherents need to perform specific tasks to bring about World's end:

– No

↳ Divine judgment event:

– Yes

↳ Restoration of the world:

– I don't know

↳ Start of a new temporal cycle:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new political system:

– I don't know

↳ Establishment of a new religious system:

– I don't know

↳ Will anyone survive the eschaton:

– I don't know

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: They used to be more solid in past times. Nowadays, they are optionally followed

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Are there centrally important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Honesty / trustworthiness / integrity:

– Yes

↳ Courage (in battle):

– I don't know

↳ Courage (generic):

– Yes

↳ Compassion / empathy / kindness / benevolence:

– Yes

↳ Mercy / forgiveness / tolerance:

– Yes

↳ Generosity / charity:

– Yes

↳ Selflessness / selfless giving:

– Yes

↳ Righteousness / moral rectitude:

– Yes

↳ Ritual purity / ritual adherence / abstention from sources of impurity:

– Yes

↳ Respectfulness / courtesy:

– Yes

↳ Familial obedience / filial piety:

– I don't know

↳ Fidelity / loyalty:

– Yes

↳ Cooperation:

– Yes

↳ Independence / creativity / freedom:

– No

↳ Moderation / frugality:

– Yes

↳ Forbearance / fortitude / patience:

– Yes

↳ Diligence / self-discipline / excellence:

– I don't know

↳ Assertiveness / decisiveness / confidence / initiative:

– No

↳ Strength (physical):

– I don't know

↳ Power / status / nobility:

– No

↳ Humility / modesty:

– Yes

↳ Contentment / serenity / equanimity:

– Yes

↳ Joyfulness / enthusiasm / cheerfulness:

– No

↳ Optimism / hope:

– Yes

↳ Gratitude / thankfulness:

– Yes

↳ Reverence / awe / wonder:

– Yes

↳ Faith / belief / trust / devotion:

– Yes

↳ Wisdom / understanding:

– I don't know

↳ Discernment / intelligence:

– No

↳ Beauty / attractiveness:

– No

↳ Cleanliness (physical) / orderliness:

– No

↳ Other important virtues advocated by the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: it is prescribed but optionally

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Notes: it is prescribed but optionally

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Notes: it is prescribed but optionally

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: optionally

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– Yes

Notes: optionally

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:
– I don't know

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.
– I don't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.
– I don't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.
– I don't know

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:
– I don't know

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:
– I don't know

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– I don't know

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: Historical circumstances were pretty complex and fluid in terms of who was in fact dominating the wider region. Although the prevailing state officially was the Principality of Achaia ruled by the Franks after the Fall of Constantinople (1204) during the Fourth Crusade, their dominance was repeatedly challenged by the Byzantines and other Latins

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– I don't know

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: optionally at schools

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– I don't know

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– I don't know

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: by the state

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Saint Nicholas "Maroulenas", Kastania, southern Greece, byzantine church, Christophidou, Athina . "The Fortified Complexes of the Kapetanies. The Example of the Troupakis - Moutrzinis Clan". In *Settlements of Mani*, 2004:162-72. Athens, 2004.